

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF EDUCATIONAL GOVERNANCE SYSTEMS IN THE UNITED STATES, CHINA, AND AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract

This article presents a comparative analysis of the educational governance systems in the United States, China, and Azerbaijan, focusing on the management structures, policy implementation, and pedagogical approaches of each country. Education systems worldwide are shaped by diverse political, social, economic, and cultural factors, leading to different governance models that influence the delivery and quality of education. The U.S. education system is decentralized, with states and local governments influencing policy and school management, while China and Azerbaijan have centralized systems, with the national government overseeing policies, curricula, and teacher management. The article compares these systems, highlighting their strengths and weaknesses, and underscores the importance of comparative studies for improving global education policies and practices.

Keywords: Educational systems, governance models, decentralization vs centralization, student participation, education management, global education comparisons.

Comparative study of educational institutions is one of the important directions of pedagogical science, and research conducted in this field serves to identify similarities and differences between the educational systems of different countries. Comparative analysis is important in terms of revealing existing problems in the field of education, studying innovative approaches and applying effective practices. This process also creates scientific foundations for improving the national education model and making strategic decisions based on international experience.

Education systems around the world are influenced by the cultural, economic, political and historical factors of each country, resulting in different approaches to educational governance. Each system is shaped by its own local needs, but the overall goal reflects a global effort to optimize educational processes and learning outcomes for individuals and societies. Its main goal is to create effective structures and practices that facilitate the delivery of quality education. The way countries organize and manage their educational institutions, and the policies that support these structures, reveal both global common goals and local specificities. This comparative analysis examines the different educational governance systems around the world, considering the balance between centralized and decentralized models, the role of the public and private sectors, and the impact of technological advances.

The application of comparative frameworks to the analysis of educational governance plays a crucial role in systematically assessing and understanding the diversity and effectiveness of education systems around the world. These frameworks allow for comparisons of educational practices across countries according to specific criteria. The comparative framework includes differences in student achievement, the efficiency of resource allocation, governance structures and the cultural relevance of curricula. By comparing these indicators across countries, stakeholders can identify patterns of performance, potential areas for reform and develop strategies that respond to both local and international educational needs. Furthermore, the use of a comparative approach helps to identify inequalities

within and between countries, provides a basis for discussion and thus contributes to ensuring equitable and quality educational opportunities for all students.

Comparison of education systems always involves both the concepts of "difference" and "similarity". On the one hand, education systems around the world can demonstrate diversity, and on the other hand, they can also demonstrate similarity. The relationship between these two concepts should not be contradictory, but rather complementary.

The educational governance landscape in the United States is a unique blend of federal, state, and local governance that reflects the country's sociopolitical diversity. U.S. education policy is decentralized, granting significant autonomy to state and local governments. The federal government sets broad standards and provides funding to promote civil rights in education and equitable access across socioeconomic lines. Thus, the U.S. educational governance system embodies a complex interplay of local autonomy, federal leadership, and responsive policies aimed at meeting diverse educational needs[1]. China's education system is highly centralized, with the government playing a key role in setting curricula, policies, and educational standards. The Ministry of Education oversees the entire education system, and its policies affect everything from school infrastructure to teacher training. Several major reforms have transformed China's education landscape in recent years. The Chinese government has historically maintained tight control over its education system. One of the key features of China's education structure is centralization, where policies, curricula, and examinations are set at the national level. This approach helps ensure uniform educational standards across the country. Local governments implement these policies, but have limited autonomy to make changes to curricula and pedagogical methods.[2]

If we compare the educational concepts between China and the United States, we can see that the modern education of the West has formed its own concept. This concept is reflected in the fact that students are the main entity in the classroom. In the US classroom, teachers always try to involve students in group discussions and cooperation, and everyone's opinions can be expressed

openly. Teachers encourage students to express their opinions and require them to clearly define their beliefs, which develops students' confidence and self-confidence. In China, under the influence of the traditional ideology of "respecting the teacher and appreciating the path", the classroom atmosphere is usually serious. Teachers and students pay attention to classroom order, respect for teachers, and not to insult them. Therefore, Chinese students often have a sense of respect and reverence for their teachers, and generally do not dare to question the subjects they teach. Similarly, traditional Chinese education pays special attention to the selection and management of teachers, but very little attention is paid to their enthusiasm and initiative in the teaching process. This is because teachers' leadership in the teaching process "It causes students to only passively accept the knowledge taught by teachers, which prevents students from learning and increasing their interests.[3]

According to the educational concept adopted in Azerbaijan in recent years, the teaching process is organized on the basis of rules that are more interactive, student-centered and meet modern requirements. This teaching process is aimed at actively involving students in the lesson, developing their independent thinking and problem-solving skills. Students are not only listeners in the classroom, but also participants in discussions and active members of group work. This approach ensures that students master their knowledge more deeply and increase their critical thinking skills.

The management of education systems depends mainly on the social, political and economic structures and education laws of each country. The forms, objectives and implementation mechanisms of education systems in different countries differ from each other. For example: The Azerbaijani education system is centrally managed. Thus, the Ministry of Education is responsible for the organization, control and development of all levels of education, the preparation of curricula, the recruitment of teachers, and the appointment of school principals. In the United States, the education system is decentralized. The management of education is mainly carried out by states and local school districts. The federal government only determines general education policy and implements financing. In the United States, curriculum, assessment and school management vary by state and school. Each state determines its own education laws and curricula. The Chinese education system is highly centralized, but some regions and universities are given a certain degree of autonomy. The Ministry of Education determines the curriculum, examination system and quality of education for the entire country. Education management is carried out by the Central People's Government. School principals are sometimes appointed with the approval of local party bodies.

When comparing the education systems of these countries, we can conclude that Azerbaijan and China use a more centralized management model, while in the United States, education management is carried out at the local level, which creates opportunities for personalized education.

The Chinese education system includes central, provincial, municipal and district-level structures responsible for education management. The Ministry of Education is responsible for formulating strategies, policies and plans for educational reform and development; formulating relevant rules and regulations and supervising their implementation. School principals are appointed by regional education management bodies. At least 10 years of teaching experience is required to become a principal.

Although the requirements for becoming a school principal in the Chinese education system vary by province or region, these requirements generally include having at least ten years of teaching experience, being a Chinese citizen living within the country's borders, and having the ability to educate ideologically, politically, and morally. The candidate's party membership and experience are also important in the selection of candidates. To become a qualified candidate, a "certificate of suitability for school principal" is required. The requirements for obtaining this certificate are a written examination, an academic qualification certificate, and work experience as a teacher. In addition to these requirements, the candidate must also have received an invitation to apply for the vacancy. In Shanghai, school principals receive leadership training for six months after being appointed. This training is conducted by universities and experts in education, management, and psychology and consists of six topics within the framework of professional standards for principals. These topics are school planning, internal management, school culture, instructional development, teacher training, and adaptation to the external environment. The program, which consists of group training, individual research projects, field trips, and mentoring of new principals by experienced principals, is held once a week "It is carried out once.

In the United States, the education system is more locally managed, allowing for flexibility to adapt to individual educational needs and giving states autonomy. China has a centralized education system, where educational policies and curricula are determined by the central government and provinces only perform an implementation function. Azerbaijan, on the other hand, has a more centralized approach, with the Ministry of Education managing all levels of education, developing curricula, and centralizing issues such as teacher recruitment. These different approaches reflect the unique characteristics and priorities of each country's education system.

Comparative study of educational institutions is one of the main directions of research in the field of education, and this process leads to many important results:

The most significant differences between the education systems of different countries are observed in the management structures and implementation of educational policies. Azerbaijan and China have highly centralized systems of educational management, where the state, especially the Ministry of Education, plays a key role. In the United States, a decentralized approach prevails, where states and local school districts implement

educational policies, which allows each region to develop educational systems that are appropriate to its own characteristics.

Comparative study of education systems allows to identify the strengths and weaknesses of each country's educational management and teaching methodology, to ensure the successful implementation of modern educational reforms, as well as to adapt international experience and strategic decisions to the local context. The differences between Azerbaijan, China and the United States show how education policy is shaped in a way that responds to local and global needs. Through comparative approaches, it is possible to create more inclusive, equitable and high-quality educational opportunities in the field of education.

Currently, educational leadership is considered a task that every teacher can perform, and it is thought that a good teacher will make a good administrator. However, educational leadership is a field that requires specialization as much as teaching. It is not realistic to expect people who have not received special training in this field to succeed in educational leadership, even if they are teachers.

Comparative study of educational institutions creates conditions for effective decision-making in education, adoption of best practices, and improvement of national education policy.

At the same time, these comparisons help identify inequalities in education systems and make strategic decisions aimed at providing more equitable and quality opportunities in the field of education. Comparative

analyses pave the way for the development of effective education policies and strategies that respond to both local and international educational needs. This process facilitates the study and application of best practices in the field of education and provides each country with a scientific basis for developing its own education system.

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